

ORGANIZATION OF HIV PREVENTION IN THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

Khudaykulova Gulnara Karimovna

Associate Professor (DSc) of the Department of Public Health and Management, Tashkent medical academy

Karimbayev Shakhrambay Dexkanbayevich

Associate Professor (PhD) of the Department of Public Health and Management, Tashkent medical academy

Mirkhamidova Sevara Mirmakhmudovna

Assistant of the Department of Public Health and Management, Tashkent medical academy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7191454>

Abstract. *This article is intended for teachers of secondary educational institutions, and may also be useful to teachers of secondary vocational education, nurses involved in the prevention of HIV infection, social educators, psychologists, methodologists and other employees of educational institutions. These methodological materials present the main approaches to the implementation of HIV prevention in the educational environment, the theoretical foundations, the regulatory framework in the field of regulation of combating the spread of HIV infection.*

Keywords: *education, teacher, scientific, methodology, prevention program.*

ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ ВИЧ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ СРЕДЕ

Аннотация. *Данная статья предназначена для учителей общеобразовательных учреждений, а также может быть полезна педагогам среднего профессионального образования, медицинским сестрам, занимающимся профилактикой ВИЧ-инфекции, социальным педагогам, психологам, методистам и другим работникам образовательных учреждений. В данных методических материалах представлены основные подходы к реализации профилактики ВИЧ в образовательной среде, теоретические основы, нормативная база в сфере регулирования противодействия распространению ВИЧ-инфекции.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, педагог, научная, методология, профилактическая программа.*

INTRODUCTION

Admittedly, HIV infection is a global health and development emergency and is one of the life-changing issues of our time. More than 25 million people have already died from it, and the number of people living with HIV continues to rise. According to UNAIDS, the number of cases in the world is over 36 million people. Every day, 7400 new cases of HIV infection are detected in the world, and 5500 people die from diseases caused by AIDS. More than 17 million children in the world have lost one or both parents. About 50,000 HIV-infected people have been identified and registered in Uzbekistan, of which more than 5,000 are children under the age of 15. The most affected cities of the Republic of Uzbekistan include industrialized regions with a higher level of income of the population: the city of Tashkent, Tashkent region, Andijan, Samarkand, Fergana, Surkhandarya. In terms of the absolute number of registered cases of HIV infection, the city of Tashkent has been steadily leading in recent years: more than 15,000 HIV infections have been registered in the Sverdlovsk region (as of the end of 2019) [1,2,3,5].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

All social and age groups of the population are involved in the epidemic process of HIV infection. Despite the pronounced trend of involvement of older age groups in the epidemic process of HIV infection, the largest proportion of HIV-infected people is among young people. Taking into account the international experience in combating the HIV epidemic and the experience gained in Uzbekistan, it can be stated that preventive education in the field of HIV infection will not only reduce the threat of infection, but also create attitudes among the younger generation to develop healthy lifestyle skills and responsible behavior.

Youth are a powerful resource for prevention action. Adhering to safe behaviors and attitudes is easier if you get used to them in advance. The need for awareness-raising activities among the population, especially among young people, who are most at risk of contracting HIV, is beyond doubt[2,5,6].

Students of all educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regardless of the form of ownership, training programs and other differences, have the right to receive adequate and complete information that would help them avoid contracting HIV. The ultimate goal of training is to motivate young people to make independent and conscious choices of behavior that prevent the risk of HIV infection.

RESULTS

Every year, more than 90% of children and adolescents go through educational institutions in the city of Tashkent. Educational institutions have a significant impact on the formation and development of the student's personality; have access to the minor's family and mechanisms to influence the family situation; have qualified specialists (teachers, psychologists, social workers, etc.), so the educational environment is the most optimal for effective preventive work in the field of HIV infection, the formation of a tolerant attitude towards HIV-infected people[3,5].

An important role in preventive education belongs to the teacher, who must have appropriate professional training and possess effective methods of preventive work. A necessary condition for increasing the professional competence of teachers is the educational and methodological support of the educational process[4,6].

According to WHO experts, it is possible to reduce the rate of development of the epidemic, first of all, by educating people in order to change their behavior in the direction of safe.

The educational environment has a great resource for direct and indirect influence on the value system of children and adolescents, which allows, depending on the target audience and expected results, to implement preventive programs of various levels. Preventive work can be carried out both through subject training and through the organization of extracurricular activities of students. The use of several approaches to prevention, which is possible only in the educational environment, significantly increases its effectiveness.

Children and adolescents in the educational environment have an unformed system of life values that can be changed by carrying out preventive work and increasing motivation for a healthy lifestyle.

Directions of preventive education in the field of HIV prevention

WHO experts and domestic scientists identify today the most promising areas of preventive education in the field of HIV prevention:

- Education and information in the field of HIV infection;

- Teaching responsible behavior to children and youth;
- Formation of conditions that support preventive activities.

DISCUSSION

HIV education and information

Education and information in the field of HIV infection involves providing comprehensive and accurate information: about the mechanism of infection, ways of transmission of HIV infection, circumstances that increase the risk of infection (drug abuse, etc.), and prevention measures.

Educational activities in educational institutions should be based on certain principles of informing about HIV, the need to comply with which has been proven by international experience and confirmed by experts from the World Health Organization (WHO).

Basic principles of HIV communication:

- Reliability of information;
- Not causing harm with incorrect (false) or misunderstood information;
- Exclusion of manipulation of information (mixing reliable and false information or presenting reliable information in a context that allows drawing false conclusions);
- Neutrality in the presentation of information;
- Informed consent to receive preventive information;
- Mutual respect in the process of informing;
- Comprehensive presentation of the problem (objectivity and multidimensionality: consideration of the physiological, social, demographic, legal, spiritual, psychological aspects);
- Personal attitude when informing about ways of protection from HIV infection;
- Adequacy to the target group (sociocultural and cognitive information);
- Creation of an existential perspective (alternativeness, hierarchy of stepped information, placement of stresses, motivation for a more complete perception of life, with values, meaning, further life perspective);
- Sympathetic attitude towards HIV-infected people.

Informing children and young people about HIV infection is carried out not only by specialists from educational and medical institutions, but also by parents. Therefore, education of parents and persons replacing them is necessary.

CONCLUSIONS

The success of any educational preventive program on HIV infection depends mainly on the preparedness of the teacher, scientific, methodological and logistical support of the educational process. When selecting information and methodological materials for a prevention program, it is important to take into account the national-regional, social and age characteristics of trainee groups, existing cultural norms, the level of training and awareness of the audience.

REFERENCES

1. Whitman, C.V., et al. 2001. Skill-based health education and lifeskills. Washington, DC, Pan-American Health Organization.
2. Impact of COVID-19 on education system in the world and in Uzbekistan // Образование: прошлое, настоящее и будущее : Материалы VIII Международной научной конференции, Краснодар, 20–23 октября 2020 года / Под редакцией И.Г. Ахметова [и др.]. – Краснодар: Новация, 2020. – P. 94-95. – EDN MTZZNP.
3. Kelly, M.J. 2000. The encounter between HIV/AIDS and education. Harare, UNESCO Sub-Regional Office for Southern Africa.
4. Мирхамидова С., Рустамова Х. Formation of the relation to the HIV infected people. – 2019.
5. Schenker, I. 2001. New challenges for school AIDS education within an evolving HIV pandemic. Prospects (Paris), vol. 30, no. 3, p. 415–34.
6. Mirkhamidova Sevara, Rustamova Hamida, Umarov Botirjon, Kamilova Dilfuza, Pakhrudinova Nigora. (2021). The Role of Nurses in Organizing Hiv Prevention Work in Educational Institutions. Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 25(2), 3079–3088. Retrieved from <https://www.annalsofrscb.ro/index.php/journal/article/view/1287>